

The Moderating Effect of the Strength of Leader Emotional Expressivity on the Direct Effect of Authentic Leadership on Follower Job Performance

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Abstract—This research attempts to explain the moderating effect of the strength of leader emotional expressivity on the direct effect of authentic leadership on follower job performance. Accordingly, quantitative data were collected through surveys from employees of service-rendering companies in Istanbul. The findings of this research have shown that the strength of leader emotional expressivity weakened the favorable effects of authentic leadership on follower job performance for highly authentic leaders. In contrast, higher leader emotional expressivity compensates for low levels of leader authenticity and increases follower job performance.

Keywords—Authentic leadership, emotions, follower job performance, leadership, leader emotional expressivity.

I. INTRODUCTION

AUTHENTIC leadership is one of the most widely researched theories in leadership. The creators of this construct assert that the decline in ethical leadership (e.g., WorldCom, Enron, Martha Stewart) together with a rise in societal troubles (e.g., September 11 terrorism, fluctuating stock values, a downturn in the economy) entails the need for authentic leadership more than in earlier times [7]. They also discuss that present frameworks are not adequate for training leaders of the future [1]. Antecedents and outcomes of authentic leadership have been explored by several researchers (e.g., [10], [18], [24], [23]). According to [4] and [8], self-knowledge is a prerequisite for authentic leadership. Reference [23] cites that leaders who have a high level of self-knowledge are clear about their values and convictions. Another antecedent for authentic leadership is self-consistency [20]. Reference [26] argues that it is of utmost importance for leaders to show consistency between their values, beliefs, and actions in order to be perceived as authentic.

Emotions are omnipresent in leader-follower interactions, originating from and affecting them [22], [25]. Because leaders have a deep influence on the activity of organizations and their insiders [30], leader emotional expositions have solid capacity to affect how their subordinates feel, think, and act [11]. In this study, the contribution of authentic leadership to follower job performance, as well as the moderating effect of the strength of leader emotional expressivity on the effect of the former on the latter was analyzed.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Authentic Leadership and Follower Job Performance

Job performance is defined as the actions and behaviors of individuals that add to organizational goals [21]. Authentic leaders act in pursuance of their values and struggle to reach openness and honesty in their relationships with followers [10], [16]. Authentic leaders can set an example and exhibit transparent decision making [1]. Setting an example manifests a leader's engagement to his or her work and supplies followers with guidance about how to stay emotionally and physically bonded and mentally awake in the course of job performance. Reference [27] debated that moral behaviors of authentic leaders eventually lead the way for their followers due to their appeal and trustworthiness as role models, which results in augmented personal identification of followers with their leaders.

Followers of authentic leaders are inclined to ascribe extraordinarily strong positive characteristics to the leaders, adopt their values and credence, and act coherently with them. For instance, [2] suggests that the actions of authentic leaders are considered by followers as being conducted by superior ethical norms and described by justice, truthfulness, and integrity when interacting with followers. Consequently, such leaders are capable of arousing values collectively held by their followers through transparency, constructiveness, and superior moral norms. Herewith, in line with the Social Exchange Theory [5], followers' willingness to manifest positive behaviors and their feeling of self-esteem and liability to give back are raised (e.g., [14], [29]). Empirical support also affirms the theoretical comprehension of why authentic leaders affect their followers' performance favorably. For instance, [27], [28] and [13] have discovered that authentic leadership behavior has a positive relation to supervisor-rated job performance. Again, [12] found that authentic leaders motivate followers through the agency of modeling and conveying a profound feeling of accountability to transfer favorable outcomes over a long-time span. Thus, we suggest the following hypothesis:

H1. Authentic leadership will have a positive contribution to follower job performance.

B. The Moderating Effect of Leader Emotional Expressivity on the Direct Effect of Authentic Leadership on Follower Job Performance

Job performance is defined as the actions and behaviors of individuals that add to organizational goals [21]. According to

our assumptions, leaders who express their true emotions will be regarded by their followers as more approachable. Based on the concept of personal identification [15]; we assume that leaders who express their emotions will be easier for followers to take as an example and to identify with, compared with leaders who keep their true feelings to themselves. Leaders who can act as a role model will also be able to show their followers which actions to take in order to contribute to the objectives of the organization, and as a result of the personal and social identification of followers with their leaders, they will try to mimic their leader's successful actions which will boost their job performance. Therefore, we suggest that in case of leaders who are lower in authenticity, a stronger leader emotional expressivity will compensate for the lack of authenticity and increase perception of followers that their leader is approachable and can be identified with, which will positively contribute to their job performance as a result of the personal and social identification with their leader. In contrast, for leaders who are already highly authentic, a strong leader emotional expressivity will be perceived by followers as the leader is expressing an overly-possessive leadership and as the leader is crossing a boundary when interacting with followers. Thus, the author proposes the hypothesis below:

H2. The direct effect of authentic leadership on follower job performance will be moderated by the strength LEE, in such a way that the relationship between authentic leadership and follower job performance is more positive for those employees whose leaders are lower on LEE as compared to those whose leaders are higher on LEE.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The aim of this study is to test the contribution of authentic leadership to follower job performance and moderating effect of the strength of LEE on the effect of authentic leadership on follower job performance.

The model depicting the hypothetical relationships is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Conceptual model of the study

Two surveys were undertaken in order to test both the contribution of authentic leadership to follower job performance and finding out the moderating effect of the strength of LEE on the relationship between authentic

leadership and follower job performance. In the employee survey, the participants were asked to rate their perception of the authenticity and emotional expressivity of their actual leaders. After the participants completed the employee survey, in the supervisor survey, the actual leaders of the participants were asked to rate the job performance of each participant. Authentic Leadership Inventory-ALI by [19] and Emotional Expressivity Scale by [17] were utilized for the participants to rate their actual leader. In addition, for the ratings of follower job performance, the in-role performance scale developed by [28] was used. The questions were read to the participants and their answers were recorded on a tablet PC.

B. Sample

A total of 258 employees working in the services departments from 32 firms and their immediate supervisors were contacted, accounting for a total of 516 responses. The average age of the employees is 28.64, ranging from 18 to 62, whereas the average age of their immediate supervisors is 34.83, ranging from 24 to 51. 94 (36.4%) of the contacted employees and 53 (20.5%) of their immediate supervisors are female. 42 (16.3%) of the contacted employees attended only elementary school, 160 (62%) are high school graduates, 54 (20.9%) attended university, and 2 (0.8%) completed higher education. In contrast, 19 (7.4%) of their immediate supervisors finished elementary school, 107 (41.5%) graduated from high school, and 132 (51.2%) are university graduates. For employees, the average working years add up to 8.20, ranging from 1 to 40. Their managers, who were their immediate supervisors, on the other hand, have averagely worked for 15.16 years, ranging from 4 to 30 years. The average tenure of employees is 3.69 years, ranging from a minimum of 1 to a maximum of 20 years. The average tenure of their team leaders is 8.19 years, ranging from 2 to 18 years. 180 (34.9%) of the total of 516 respondents are from the retail industry, 98 (19%) work in the food industry, 96 (18.6%) come from the textile industry, 34 (6.6%) work in the IT sector, 24 (4.7%) are from the electronics industry, 20 (3.9%) work in the financial industry, 16 (3.1%) come from the construction industry, another 16 (3.1%) work in the paper industry, and again another 16 (3.1%) are hired in the agricultural industry, 12 (2.3%) deal with trade, and lastly 4 (0.8%) are employed in customer services.

C. Hypothesis Testing

Regression analysis has been undertaken in order to test the contribution of authentic leadership to follower job performance. For the regression analysis, two models have been created. The first model tests the effect of control variables on the dependent variable, and the second model tests the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable, in addition to the effect of the control variables on the dependent variable.

For the measurement of the direct effect of authentic leadership on follower job performance, the multiple regression models are expressed as follows:

$$\text{Model 1: Follower job performance} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * (\text{Age}) +$$

$$\beta_2*(Gender) + \beta_3*(Tenure) + \epsilon$$

$$\text{Model 2: Follower job performance} = \beta_0 + \beta_1*(Age) + \beta_2*(Gender) + \beta_3*(Tenure) + \beta_4*(Authentic leadership) + \epsilon$$

In these models; age, gender, and tenure are control variables.

Tables 1 and 2 below demonstrate the multiple regression analysis results for the second dependent variable, follower job performance:

TABLE I

MODEL SUMMARY OF THE MULTIPLE REGRESSION ANALYSIS FOR THE CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHENTIC LEADERSHIP TO FOLLOWER JOB PERFORMANCE

Model Summary										
Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					ΔR^2	ΔF	df	df2	Sig.	
1	.17	.03	.02	.90	.03	2.63	3	254	.05	1.73
2	.81	.66	.65	.53	.63	468.23	1	253	.00	3

TABLE II

REGRESSION COEFFICIENTS FOR THE CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHENTIC LEADERSHIP TO FOLLOWER JOB PERFORMANCE

Model	Ind. Variables	Unstd. Coefficients		Std. Coeff.	t	Sig.
		β	Std. Error			
		β				
1	(Constant)	4.65	.31		14.78	.00
	Age	-.02	.01	-.12	-1.39	.17
	Gender	-.18	.12	-.10	-1.57	.12
	Tenure	-.01	.02	-.02	-.28	.78
2	(Constant)	1.04	.25		4.15	.00
	Age	-.01	.01	-.07	-1.37	.17
	Gender	-.13	.07	-.07	-1.83	.07
	Tenure	.01	.01	.05	.98	.33
	Authentic leadership	.84	.04	.80	21.64	.00

As observed from the above tables, authentic leadership ($\beta = 0.80$, $t = 21.64$, $p < .05$) significantly predicts follower job performance. This model explains 65% of the variance ($p < .05$). Therefore, H1 (Authentic leadership will have a positive contribution to follower job performance) is supported.

For the moderation analysis, two models have been created. Along with the control variables, the independent variables of the regression are independent variable, moderator, and the interaction between independent variable and moderator. The first model tests the effect of the control variables on the dependent variable, and the second model tests the effect of the independent variable, the moderator, and the interaction between independent variable and moderator on the dependent variable, in addition to the effect of the control variables on the dependent variable.

The multiple regression models for the moderating effect of LEE on the relationship between authentic leadership and follower job performance are demonstrated as follows:

$$\text{Model 1: Follower job performance} = \beta_0 + \beta_1*(Age) +$$

$$\beta_2*(Gender) + \beta_3*(Tenure) + \epsilon$$

$$\text{Model 2: Follower job performance} = \beta_0 + \beta_1*(Age) + \beta_2*(Gender) + \beta_3*(Tenure) + \beta_4*(ZAuthentic leadership) + \beta_5*(ZLEE) + \epsilon$$

$$\text{Model 3: Follower job performance} = \beta_0 + \beta_1*(Age) + \beta_2*(Gender) + \beta_3*(Tenure) + \beta_4*(ZAuthentic leadership) + \beta_5*(ZLEE) + \beta_6*(ZAuthentic leadership * ZLEE) + \epsilon$$

In these models; age, gender, and tenure are control variables.

Table 3 and 4 below show the moderating effect of LEE on the relationship between authentic leadership and follower job performance.

TABLE III

MODEL SUMMARY OF THE MULTIPLE REGRESSION ANALYSIS FOR THE MODERATION OF LEE ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN AUTHENTIC LEADERSHIP AND FOLLOWER JOB PERFORMANCE

Model Summary										
Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					ΔR^2	ΔF	df	df2	Sig.	
1	.17	.03	.02	.90	.03	2.63	3	254	.05	1.73
2	.83	.69	.68	.51	.66	247.15	2	252	.00	2
3	.83	.69	.68	.51	.02	14.67	1	251	.00	2

TABLE IV

REGRESSION COEFFICIENTS FOR THE MODERATION OF LEE ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN AUTHENTIC LEADERSHIP AND FOLLOWER JOB PERFORMANCE

Model	Ind. Variables	Unstd. Coefficients		Std. Coeff.	t	Sig.
		β	Std. Error			
		β				
1	(Constant)	4.65	.31		14.78	.00
	Age	-.02	.01	-.12	-1.39	.17
	Gender	-.18	.12	-.10	-1.57	.12
	Tenure	-.01	.02	-.02	-.28	.78

2	(Constant)	1.58	.29		5.51	.00
	Age	-.01	.01	-.06	-1.20	.23
	Gender	-.10	.07	-.05	-1.48	.14
	Tenure	.01	.01	.04	.91	.36
	ZAuthentic leadership	.52	.07	.50	7.15	.00
	ZLEE	.21	.05	.24	4.35	.00
3	(Constant)	4.35	.18		24.05	.00
	Age	-.01	.01	-.06	-1.20	.23
	Gender	-.10	.07	-.05	-1.48	.14
	Tenure	.01	.01	.04	.91	.36
	ZAuthentic leadership	.46	.06	.50	7.15	.00
	ZLEE	.22	.05	.24	4.35	.00
	ZAuthentic leadership*	-.17	.04	-.20	-3.83	.00
	ZLEE					

As seen in the tables above, LEE ($\beta = -0.20$, $t = -3.83$, $p < .05$) moderates the relationship between authentic leadership and follower job performance. While LEE has a positive contribution ($\beta = .24$, $t = 4.35$, $p < .05$) to the dependent variable of job performance, the interaction of LEE with authentic leadership is negative. The model explains 69% of the variance ($p < .05$) in the dependent variable. Therefore, H2 (The direct effect of authentic leadership on follower job performance will be moderated by the strength of LEE, in such a way that the relationship between authentic leadership and follower job performance is more positive for those employees whose leaders are lower on LEE as compared to those whose leaders are higher on LEE) is supported.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

As hypothesized and found in H1, followers of authentic leaders benefit from greater job performance. Reference [3] suggests that authentic leadership may be thought of as a metaphor for professionally effective, ethically sound, and consciously reflective practices in educational administration. Naturally, these characteristics of authentic leaders will have a positive contribution to their followers' job performance.

As hypothesized and found in H2, LEE moderates the direct effect of authentic leadership on follower job performance. Although LEE has a significant positive contribution to follower job performance; parallel to our expectations, higher LEE weakens the positive contributions of authentic leadership to follower job performance for leaders who are strongly authentic. We assumed that leaders who express their true emotions would be regarded by their followers as more approachable and easier for followers to take as an example and to identify with. Therefore, they could act as role models for their followers and show them which actions to take in order to contribute to the objectives of the organization. The findings indicate that LEE has a positive contribution to follower job performance. Also, in parallel to our propositions, the strength of LEE weakened the contributions of authentic leadership to follower job performance for leaders who are highly authentic. Namely, if leaders are highly emotionally expressive and if they are at the same time strongly authentic, then the interaction of these two strong qualities results in

weaker positive contributions of authentic leadership to follower job performance. On the other hand, higher LEE compensates for the low levels of authenticity in terms of increasing follower job performance.

The combination of very strong authenticity by the leader and being highly emotionally expressive may result in an overly-possessive kind of leader-follower relationship in the eyes of the followers, such as in case of an overly possessive relationship between adults and children, where adults have a wish to be fully in control of the situation and attempt to make sure that they will get their fair share of benefits from the relationship [9]. Such a view of the leader by the followers may contribute to the decrease in follower job performance. Namely, followers may think that their leader is crossing a boundary with them by being highly emotionally expressive in addition to being strongly authentic.

The results of this study also highlight the fact that there can be a LEE premium, in such a way that leaders who are not strongly authentic, however, if they are highly emotionally expressive, this high level of emotional expressivity can compensate for their lack of authenticity. Therefore, followers may commit to a highly emotionally expressive leader even if this leader lacks authenticity. The existence of a high level of LEE can thus alter the charisma of the leader in parallel with the findings by [6], where mood contagion, through the expression of positive emotions, was one of the psychological mechanisms by which charismatic leaders influence followers.

V. DIRECTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

This study does not explain the reason why the strength of LEE weakened the contributions of authentic leadership to follower job performance for leaders who are highly authentic. Therefore, we suggest that follower characteristics such as individualism or egalitarianism values can be studied in future research in order to be able to interpret the moderation of LEE better. We think that follower characteristics, which were beyond the scope of this research, can play a role in the negative moderating effect of LEE on the relationship between authentic leadership and follower job performance. For example, followers, if they share an egalitarian point of view, might more strongly regard the highly emotionally expressive leader as crossing a boundary and become intimidated by that leader.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Avolio, B. J., & Gardner, W. L. (2005). Authentic leadership development: Getting to the root of positive forms of leadership. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 16(3), 315-338.
- [2] Avolio, B. J., Gardner, W. L., Walumbwa, F. O., Luthans, F., & 88May, D. R. (2004). Unlocking the mask: A look at the process by which authentic leaders impact follower attitudes and behaviors. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 15(6), 801-823.
- [3] Begley, P. T. (2001). In pursuit of authentic school leadership practices. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 4(4),

- 353-365.
- [4] Bennis, W. (2003). *On Becoming a Leader*. Cambridge, MA: Perseus Publishing.
- [5] Blau, P. (1964). *Exchange and power in social life*. New York: Wiley.
- [6] Bono, J. E. & Ilies, R. (2006). Charisma, positive emotions and mood contagion. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 17(4), 317-334.
- [7] Cooper, C. D., Scandura, T. A. & Schriesheim, C. A. (2005). Looking forward but learning from our past: Potential challenges to developing authentic leadership theory and authentic leaders. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 16(3), 475-493.
- [8] Eriksen, M. (2009). Authentic leadership: Practical reflexivity, self awareness, and self-authorship. *Journal of Management Education*, 33(6), 747-771.
- [9] Flasher, J. (1978). *Adolescence*. NY: Roslyn Heights.
- [10] Gardner, W. L., Avolio, B. J., Luthans, F., May, D. R., & Walumbwa, F. (2005). Can you see the real me? A self based model of authentic leader and follower development. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 16(3), 343-372.
- [11] George, J. M. (2000). Emotions and leadership: The role of emotional intelligence. *Human Relations*, 53(8), 1027-1055.
- [12] George, W. (2003). *Authentic leadership: Rediscovering the secrets to creating lasting value*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- [13] Gül, H. & Alacalar, A. (2014). Otantik liderlik ile izleyicilerin duygusal bağlılıkları ve performansları arasındaki ilişkiler üzerine bir araştırma. *Akademik Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 2(5), 540-550.
- [14] Ilies, R., Morgeson, F. P., & Nahrgang, J. D. (2005). Authentic leadership and eudaemonic well-being: Understanding leader-follower outcomes. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 16(3), 373-394.
- [15] Kark, R., & Shamir, B. (2002). The dual effect of transformational leadership: Priming relational and collective selves and further effects on followers. In B. J. Avolio & F. J. Yammarino (Eds.), *Transformational and Charismatic Leadership: The Road Ahead 10th Anniversary Edition* (pp. 77-101). Bingley: Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- [16] Kernis, M. H. (2003). Toward a conceptualization of optimal self-esteem. *Psychological Inquiry*, 14(1), 1-26.
- [17] Kring, A. M., Smith, D. A., & Neale, J. M. (1994). Individual Differences in Dispositional Expressiveness: Development and Validation of the Emotional Expressivity Scale. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 66(5), 934-949.
- [18] Luthans, F., & Avolio, B. J. (2003). Authentic leadership development. In K. S. Cameron, J. E. Dutton, & R. E. Quinn (Eds.), *Positive organizational scholarship: Foundations of a new discipline* (pp. 241-261). San Francisco: Barrett-Koehler.
- [19] Neider, L. L., Schriesheim, C. A. (2011). The authentic leadership inventory (ALI): Development and empirical tests. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 22(6), 1146-1164.
- [20] Peus, C., Wesche, J. S., Streicher, B., Braun, S. & Frey, D. (2012). Authentic Leadership: An Empirical Test of Its Antecedents, Consequences, and Mediating Mechanisms. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 107(3), 331-348.
- [21] Rotundo, M., & Sackett, P. R. (2002). The relative importance of task, citizenship and counterproductive performance to global ratings of job performance: a policy-capturing approach. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87(1), 66-80.
- [22] Rubin, R. S., Munz, D. C., & Bommer, W. H. (2005). Leading from within: The effects of emotion recognition and personality on transformational leadership behavior. *Academy of Management Journal*, 48(5), 845-858.
- [23] Shamir, B., & Eilam, G. (2005). What's your story? A life-stories approach to authentic leadership development. *Leadership Quarterly*, 16(3), 395-417.
- [24] Sparrowe, R. T. (2005). Authentic leadership and the narrative self. *Leadership Quarterly*, 16(3), 419-439.
- [25] Sy, T., Côté, S., & Saavedra, R. (2005). The contagious leader: Impact of the leader's mood on the mood of group members, group affective tone, and group processes. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 90(2), 295-305.
- [26] Walumbwa, F. O., Avolio, B. J., Gardner, W. L., Wernsing, T. S., & Peterson, S. J. (2008). Authentic leadership: Development and validation of a theory-based measure. *Journal of Management*, 34(1), 89-126.
- [27] Walumbwa, F. O., Christensen, A. L., & Hailey, F. (2011). Authentic leadership and the knowledge economy. *Organizational Dynamics*, 40(2), 110-118.
- [28] Williams, L. J., & Anderson, S. E. (1991). Job satisfaction and organizational commitment as predictors of organizational citizenship and in-role behavior. *Journal of Management*, 17(3), 601-617.
- [29] Yukl, G. A. (1994). Perspectives on effective leadership behavior. In *Leadership in Organizations* (3rd ed., pp. 53-79). Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- [30] Yukl, G. A. (2005). *Leadership in organizations* (6th ed.). New York: Prentice Hall.